

Shaping the Future of Primary Care: Health Professionals' Attitudes and Preferences for Designing New Models of Care

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SUMMARY

Although the crucial role of health professionals in transforming primary care is widely acknowledged, existing research to date has provided limited insights into their attitudes towards health promotion, interprofessional collaboration, and innovativeness. This dissertation systematically investigates the attitudes and preferences of health professionals regarding new models of care. It addresses four central knowledge gaps by examining health professionals' willingness to engage in health-promoting practices, their attitudes towards interprofessional collaboration and responsibility-sharing, their individual innovativeness, and their preferences concerning the design of new models of care.

To this end, a large-scale cross-sectional study was conducted in 2022, based on a nationwide web-based survey among pharmacists, physicians, medical practice assistants, nurses, and physiotherapists – the five largest health professional groups in Swiss primary care. In total, 4,063 health professionals participated.

The dissertation identifies a clear willingness among health professionals, particularly non-physicians, to embrace enhanced responsibilities, health promotion activities, interprofessional collaboration, and innovation. Professionals across all groups favour collaborative, interprofessional models featuring shared decision-making processes and organisational structures such as health centres and networks, moving beyond traditional general practitioner-centred care.

These findings highlight that new primary care models, informed by professionals' preferences, could address systemic challenges such as workforce shortages while enhancing the attractiveness of careers in primary care. By aligning the development of models of care with professionals' preferences, this dissertation provides empirical evidence to inform the sustainable transformation of primary care. These insights offer guidance for policymakers, educators, healthcare providers, and researchers aiming to implement sustainable primary care structures.

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

APN	Advanced Practice Nurse
CFIR	Consolidated Framework for Implementation Research
DCE	Discrete choice experiment
EPD	Electronic Patient Record
GP	General practitioner
IPC	Interprofessional collaboration
NCD	Non-communicable disease
Obsan	Swiss Health Observatory

CHAPTER 1 Introduction

1.1 Background

This chapter sets out the context in which this dissertation was developed. It highlights the challenges faced by health professionals working in Swiss primary care and the impacts of these challenges on patients to date. It also presents key developments and initiatives that have emerged in recent years to address these challenges through new models of care. Furthermore, this chapter reviews the current state of research on health professionals' attitudes and preferences regarding their work. Based on this, it identifies existing knowledge gaps and explains why addressing them is essential for shaping the future of primary care.

1.1.1 Challenges in Primary Care

Health professionals in primary care bear substantial responsibility, as the majority of all health-related problems are resolved at this level (Tandjung et al., 2015). As a result, health professionals in primary care play a pivotal role in promoting population health and managing chronic conditions (Starfield et al., 2005; World Health Organization, 2008). They face numerous and growing challenges, including workforce shortages, rising demand due to ageing populations, the burden of increasing levels of chronic disease, and escalating cost pressures place significant strain on the primary care workforce (The Lancet Global Health, 2023).

In Switzerland, projections indicate that by 2029, only one third of the demand for nursing and care professionals will be met (Merçay et al., 2021). Recruitment difficulties, unfilled vacancies, and growing reliance on foreign-trained professionals are exacerbating staffing pressures (Burla et al., 2022; Merçay et al., 2021). Moreover, increasing administrative workloads and complex job demands have contributed to dissatisfaction and a high rate of attrition (Bolliger et al., 2016; Kraft et al., 2016; Kronenberg & Streit, 2019; Lobsiger & Liechti, 2021; Siroka, 2022).

These developments have tangible effects on patients in primary care settings (Clausen & Kraft, 2021). In some regions, up to 60% of general practitioner (GP) practices are no longer accepting new patients due to exhausted capacity (Stierli et al., 2021), leading to overuse of emergency departments for non-urgent issues (Bodenmann et al., 2021; Diserens et al., 2015). High turnover rates among health professionals are limiting primary care providers' ability to develop relationships with their patients which, in turn, can worsen patients' health outcomes and their future use of primary care services (Sabety et al., 2021). In parallel, healthcare is becoming increasingly expensive for the population as the share of gross domestic product spent on healthcare continues to rise (BFS, 2022; OECD/EU, 2018), making efficiency a

central but challenging imperative for health professionals (Trageser & Gschwend, 2019; Wittwer et al., 2016).

The integration of technology introduces an additional layer of complexity. Health professionals must integrate digital tools and new technologies into practice while adapting their workflows, often without adequate support or training (SBFI, 2017). Although these developments offer opportunities for professional growth and task diversification, they also demand high levels of adaptability, resilience and innovativeness.

Demographic changes, an ageing population and the increasing amount of care and therapy required place additional demands on health professionals in primary care (Hahn et al., 2013). By 2050, more than a quarter of Switzerland's population will be over 65, with the number of people aged 80 and above more than doubling (BFS, 2020). Therefore, it is to be expected that chronic conditions and non-communicable diseases (NCDs), which accounted for 80% of healthcare expenditure in 2011 (Huber & Wieser, 2018; Wieser et al., 2018), will continue to become more prevalent in the future.

An increasing challenge is the widespread sense of disillusionment among health professionals – not only in primary care, but across the healthcare system as a whole. As shown in a large-scale survey of the *Swiss Cohort of Healthcare Professionals and Informal Caregivers* (Gilles et al., 2025), many health professionals in Switzerland perceive a disconnect between political decision-making and the realities of working on the frontline (Gilles et al., 2025). Respondents expressed frustration over their limited influence on healthcare policy. The study identified growing distrust in the healthcare system and its leadership structures as a key concern. This is particularly evident among younger professionals, who seem less willing to prioritise professional demands over their personal well-being (Richmond, 2022; Zuzelo, 2023). These findings point to structural inefficiencies and an excessive reliance on individual overcommitment rather than sustainable workforce strategies (Boy & Sürmeli, 2023). While these results are not specific to primary care, they highlight systemic conditions that underscore the importance of meaningfully involving health professionals in the future design of healthcare delivery.

1.1.2 New Models of Care

In response to these challenges, various stakeholders in Switzerland – including the federal government, cantons, professional associations, and researchers – have been debating, exploring and piloting new models of care (BAG, 2025a; Balthasar et al., 2024; Carron et al., 2021; fmc, 2020; GDK & BAG, 2012; Gesundheits- und Sozialkommission des Grossen Rates, 2025; Kaufmann et al., 2021; Rawlinson et al., 2021; SAMW, 2019). This includes an analysis of the attitudes and preferences of the general population regarding new models of primary care (Kaufmann et al., 2021). It also includes an action plan that presents an adaptable care

network known as the *Gesundheitsnetz für alle – pour tous – per tutti (Health Network for All)* as a vision for sustainable healthcare (Balthasar et al., 2024). These transformational efforts aim to strengthen primary care while making it more attractive and sustainable for the workforce (Balthasar et al., 2024; fmc, 2020; GDK & BAG, 2012; Giger & De Geest, 2008).

Policy frameworks increasingly promote the reorganisation of primary care through skill-mix adjustments – that is, by optimising the distribution of tasks and responsibilities across professional groups (GDK & BAG, 2012). These reforms aim to ensure that services are delivered in the most appropriate setting and by the most suitable professionals (Giger & De Geest, 2008). Enhancing interprofessional collaboration (IPC), expanding the scope of practice for non-physician health professionals, and rethinking traditional role boundaries are seen as key strategies to improve care quality, accessibility, and system sustainability (Giger & De Geest, 2008). How specific tasks and responsibilities – such as initial patient contact, development of treatment plans, and clinical decision-making – should be distributed within interprofessional teams is the subject of political debate. In this context, evidence suggests that direct access to non-medical professionals can improve both the quality and efficiency of care (Goodwin & Hendrick, 2016; Ojha et al., 2014), while joint decision-making within teams can improve outcomes in complex cases and increase job satisfaction (BAG, 2021; SAMW, 2020).

In line with the objectives of reorganising primary care, several new models of care have emerged in Switzerland in recent years. A common feature of these models is the involvement of professionals such as Advanced Practice Nurses (APNs), medical practice assistants and physiotherapists, who increasingly perform tasks beyond their traditional roles (Ansorg et al., 2022; Eissler & Zumstein-Shaha, 2023; Essig, 2022; Gysin et al., 2019, 2020; Josi et al., 2020; Josi & Bianchi, 2019; Josi & De Pietro, 2019; Schlunegger et al., 2024; Schönenberger et al., 2020; Sottas et al., 2019; Winteler et al., 2022; Zumstein-Shaha et al., 2022). These professionals increasingly take on tasks traditionally performed by physicians, highlighting their potential to alleviate workload pressures and contribute to primary care (Josi et al., 2020). The innovative primary care models mentioned above also include new organisational forms such as multiprofessional group practices, integrated health centres, and regional health networks (Käppeli et al., 2024; Trageser et al., 2017). These health networks can be effective tools for improving quality of care and patient outcomes across a range of clinical disciplines while controlling costs (Brown et al., 2016; Trageser et al., 2017).

These new models of care often encounter barriers such as inadequate reimbursement mechanisms and resistance to role changes embedded within professional cultures (Rawlinson et al., 2021). Their successful implementation relies on health professionals' willingness and ability to adopt new roles and engage in IPC (Josi et al., 2020; Rawlinson et

al., 2021). To support this process, systematic knowledge is needed on how health professionals themselves assess and prioritise the key elements of new models of care.

1.1.3 Attitudes of Health Professionals

To overcome the challenges outlined above – such as workforce shortages, an ageing population, the rising prevalence of chronic diseases, and increasing cost pressures – health professionals require more than clinical expertise. Their willingness and ability to support patients in adopting health-promoting behaviours, to strengthen IPC, to take on or relinquish responsibility for clinical decision-making, and to embrace innovation are increasingly recognised as core professional competencies. These competencies are essential to manage the growing complexity of care, rising administrative demands, and the integration of new technologies into practice. They are also considered critical to ensuring accessible, high-quality, and sustainable service delivery in the face of demographic changes, multimorbidity, and evolving expectations regarding person-centred and team-based care (Giger & De Geest, 2008). However, the existing literature does not sufficiently capture the full range of underlying attitudes that shape how professionals respond to these demands.

Given the strong emphasis on the prevention of NCDs in national health strategies, health professionals play a pivotal role in the implementation of health promotion (Johansson et al., 2010). A key factor influencing the extent to which health professionals participate in health promotion activities – yet one that is insufficiently addressed in existing literature – is the role of professional beliefs. These beliefs reflect what professionals consider to be their core responsibilities and are significant in influencing their approach, values and behaviours as well as their interactions with patients, colleagues, and the healthcare system as a whole (Rubio-Valera et al., 2014). Professional beliefs can be categorised into a pathogenetic perspective, which focuses on curing disease and does not consider increased risk as requiring treatment, and a salutogenetic perspective, which emphasises maintaining and promoting health through a holistic view of patients and health-promoting factors (Pelikan, 2017; Rubio-Valera et al., 2014). These beliefs may significantly influence health professionals' willingness to engage in health-promoting practices.

Similarly, while IPC is widely endorsed as a cornerstone of effective primary care (Espinoza et al., 2018; Körner et al., 2015; Labrague et al., 2022; Lee et al., 2021; Wagner et al., 2017), the reluctance of physicians to share responsibility remains a major barrier to its implementation (Whitehead, 2007). In many healthcare systems, physicians continue to act as the sole decision-makers, while non-physician health professionals have limited authority in clinical decision-making (Baker et al., 2011; D'Amour et al., 2008; King & Ross, 2004; Paradis & Whitehead, 2015; van Duin et al., 2022). To address this imbalance, educational interventions are increasingly being developed to encourage both physicians and non-physician

professionals to take on or relinquish responsibility within collaborative care settings (Teuwen et al., 2022). Nevertheless, there is currently no empirical evidence regarding whether a relationship exists between professionals' willingness to take on or relinquish responsibility and their willingness to strengthen in IPC. If such a relationship could be established, targeted educational programmes could be used to improve IPC by fostering responsibility-sharing across professions.

In addition, the ability to respond to ongoing challenges in primary care depends critically on harnessing the innovative capacity of the health workforce. *Individual innovativeness* – the personal capacity to adopt and implement new ideas (Rogers & Shoemaker, 1971) – is increasingly important considering technological advances and organisational change. To date, innovation research in health professions has largely focused on nurses as non-physician professionals. In contrast, policy debates have primarily centred on physicians as gatekeepers, decision-makers and central actors in innovation leadership (Berwick, 2003; Cain & Mittman, 2002; Christensen et al., 2017; Herzlinger, 2006; Huynh et al., 2023; Schiavone, 2020; Varkey et al., 2008). Given the growing shortage of physicians and nurses and the rising prevalence of multimorbidity, it is essential to extend research on individual innovativeness to a broader range of health professionals. Currently, there is limited evidence regarding the levels of innovativeness across different professions and how these differences may affect the transformation of healthcare delivery.

1.1.4 Preferences of Health Professionals

In order to successfully and sustainably introduce new models of care despite the above mentioned barriers such as limited reimbursement schemes and resistance to role changes within professional cultures (Rawlinson et al., 2021), it is important to not only consider the attitudes but also the preferences of health professionals. Implementation science frameworks emphasise that these factors are crucial for the acceptance and adoption of innovations, such as new models of care (Damschroder et al., 2022; Proctor et al., 2011). So far, there have been few studies conducted on the preferences of health professionals working in primary care.

Previous studies in the Swiss context have focused primarily on factors influencing workforce retention of health professionals in order to address the challenge of workforce shortages. These include job satisfaction and working conditions such as work-life balance, workload, role clarity, teamwork, leadership quality, and remuneration (Addor et al., 2016; Fischbacher et al., 2024; Gilles et al., 2025; Möckli et al., 2025; Peter et al., 2024; Roth, Gilles, et al., 2024; Roth, Le Saux, et al., 2024; Schaffert et al., 2015; Schaffert & Robin, 2019). Others studies address the challenges posed by digital transformation, such as technostress (Golz et al., 2021). Further studies have examined work-related quality of life, presenteeism and occupational

health of health professionals (Gerber et al., 2024; Golz et al., 2024; Martins et al., 2025; Peter et al., 2023). These studies tend to focus on specific professional groups – mainly nurses – and are often limited to institutional or inpatient care settings. Most of them do not capture perspectives of a broader range of professional groups, and none of them capture preferences concerning future models of care.

Internationally, various studies have investigated health professionals' job preferences, particularly in relation to workplace characteristics such as geographic location, infrastructure, training opportunities, or managerial support (McAuliffe et al., 2016; Mumbauer et al., 2021; Rockers et al., 2012). These studies are predominantly based in non-European countries and often employ experimental designs to identify determinants of employment decisions in rural or underserved regions. In Turkey, for example, studies have examined medical students' preferences for their future mandatory service in the public sector (Tozduman & Sözmen, 2024), as well as the preferences of practising physicians and nurses regarding working conditions and locational factors (İşlek & Şahin, 2023).

In addition, several studies have addressed the preferences of health professionals regarding attributes of models of care (Berendsen et al., 2007; Cheung et al., 2013; Leach et al., 2018). These, too, often focus on specific professional groups or care approaches. For example, a cross-sectional study in Australia examined how healthcare providers and consumers perceive integrative healthcare models (Leach et al., 2018). In the Netherlands, qualitative studies explored the motivations of GPs (Berendsen et al., 2007) and medical specialists (Berendsen et al., 2006) to participate in collaborative care models. These studies aimed to better understand the drivers for initiating and maintaining IPC in outpatient settings.

The analysis of existing literature shows that these international studies on preferences of health professionals predominantly investigate workplace-related characteristics and focus on specific regional or sectoral contexts. While many of these studies provide valuable insights into strategies for addressing workforce shortages, recruitment and retention, they rarely examine the preferences of health professionals regarding the design of care models – particularly within the scope of primary care. Where such preferences are addressed, the focus tends to lie on specific professional groups, clinical areas, or care approaches. The transferability of these findings to the Swiss context is limited, as the underlying health systems differ substantially.

1.1.5 Knowledge Gaps and Research Rationale

The transformation of primary care delivery is a complex undertaking that requires not only structural reforms and political will, but also the active engagement of health professionals across different professions. Despite growing recognition of the importance of professional attitudes and preferences in shaping the uptake and implementation of new models of care,

current research provides only limited insight into these aspects. While numerous studies have addressed working conditions, job satisfaction, or workforce retention, few studies have examined how professionals perceive their role and responsibilities in future models of care or how willing they are to adopt new roles and tasks or to strengthen IPC.

Moreover, although preferences of the Swiss population regarding models of care have been systematically explored (Kaufmann et al., 2021), comparable studies involving health professionals remain scarce (Balthasar et al., 2017). This lack of empirical evidence on health professionals' preferences regarding the design of new models of care constrains the development of such models that have the potential not only to be clinically effective and patient-centred, but also aligned with the preferences and capacities of the health workforce. Previous research has focused either on specific professional groups, regions or clinical areas, or on particular approaches to care, which limits the applicability of the findings to the Swiss healthcare system, and to primary care in particular.

To ensure that future models of care are both implementable and sustainable – meaning resilient enough to withstand the challenges facing primary care and responsive to the needs of health professionals – it is essential to understand the attitudes of health professionals across different professional groups regarding core aspects of care delivery such as health promotion, responsibility-sharing, IPC, and innovativeness. Without this understanding, efforts to redesign primary care risk overlooking critical levers of competencies, motivation, and innovation capacity within the workforce.

This dissertation seeks to address these shortcomings by focusing on five major health professions active in Swiss primary care – pharmacists, physicians, medical practice assistants, nurses, and physiotherapists¹ – and by systematically investigating their attitudes and preferences regarding new models of care. In doing so, it contributes to filling four central knowledge gaps:

- Limited understanding of health professionals' willingness to engage in health-promoting practices and the influence of professional beliefs
- Lack of empirical evidence on the relationship between attitudes towards responsibility-sharing and willingness to strengthen IPC
- Sparse data on individual innovativeness across different professional groups within primary care

¹ The professional groups are listed in the original order used in the German-language survey materials, rather than alphabetically in English. This order has been retained throughout the dissertation and related publications to ensure consistency in terminology, statistical reporting, and variable coding.

- Insufficient knowledge of health professionals' preferences regarding the design of new models of care, including the distribution of responsibilities, clinical decision-making processes, and organisational structures

Addressing these gaps is essential for developing care models that respond to population health needs while also strengthening the sustainability and attractiveness of careers in primary care (GDK & BAG, 2012; Giger & De Geest, 2008). Models that reflect the perspectives of those who deliver care are more likely to be accepted, effectively implemented, and resilient in the face of future health system challenges (Damschroder et al., 2022; Proctor et al., 2011).

1.2 Objectives and Institutional Context of the Dissertation

This chapter outlines the objectives of the dissertation, presenting both the overarching objective and four specific aims. It also provides an overview of how these aims are addressed across the dissertation's components, including peer-reviewed publications, a national report, and a policy brief. In addition, the chapter places the dissertation in the broader context of the *Health2040* research initiative, which provides the academic and institutional framework for this work. To complement the textual overview, a graphical illustration is included to depict the overall aim, the studies and reports with their specific research focuses, and the structure of the dissertation (Figure 1).

1.2.1 Overall Objective and Specific Aims

This dissertation addresses the above-mentioned gaps in knowledge and pursues several objectives. The overarching objective of this dissertation is to provide empirical evidence for new models of care, based on the attitudes and preferences of health professionals, to inform the design of innovative and sustainable models of care for the future. In this dissertation, *innovative* refers to models that provide new approaches to organisation, professional roles, and collaboration. *Sustainable* refers to models that are resilient enough to withstand the challenges facing primary care.

To achieve the overarching objective, the dissertation focuses on four specific aims:

1. Investigating associations between professional beliefs and willingness to engage in health-promoting practices
2. Examining associations between willingness to take on or relinquish more responsibility and the willingness to strengthen IPC
3. Investigating associations between profession-related characteristics and individual innovativeness
4. Assess preferences of health professionals regarding the design of responsibilities for first contact, development and implementation of treatment plans as well as the type of decision making and the type of organisation in primary care

In order to address these aims, the dissertation comprises different studies and reports. The main part of the dissertation consists of three studies that have been or will be published in peer-reviewed scientific journals (chapters 2 to 4). These studies address the specific aims 1 to 3 mentioned above. The main part also includes a report for the Swiss Health Observatory (Obsan), which addresses the above-mentioned aim 4 (chapter 5). The methods used and the central findings from the three studies and the Obsan report are described and discussed in the following subchapters of chapter 1. To contribute to the health policy debate on the design of new models of care, a policy brief is also included as part of this dissertation (chapter 5).

1.2.2 Academic and Institutional Context

This dissertation is embedded within the *Health2040* research initiative, a forward-looking programme established to generate scientific foundations for sustainable primary care in Switzerland (University of Lucerne & Interface Politikstudien Forschung Beratung AG, 2025). The initiative addresses the anticipated transformations in primary care including demographic change, increasing prevalence of chronic illness, cost pressures, growing service demands, and technological advances, with the goal of ensuring a resilient model of care that is equipped to withstand the challenges of the future.

Health2040 represents a collaborative partnership between the University of Lucerne's Faculty of Health Sciences and Medicine, Interface Lucerne, and the Swiss Learning Health System (SLHS). This partnership brings together academic expertise, practice-oriented insights, and policy perspectives to develop evidence-based solutions aimed at strengthening the Swiss healthcare system in the face of evolving challenges.

Health2040 is supported by an advisory group comprising representatives from key Swiss healthcare institutions: the Federal Office of Public Health, Competence Network for Health Workforce, Curafutura, Swiss Medical Association, Conference of Cantonal Health Directors, Swiss Health Observatory, National Association of Health Professions, Swiss Nurses Association, Spitex Switzerland, Swiss Pharmacists Association, Pharmaceutical Care Research Group of the University of Basel, Swiss Young Pharmacists Group, and the Institute for Primary Care & Community Care of the University of Lucerne. This diverse representation ensures that multiple perspectives from across the Swiss healthcare landscape informed the research process.

The *Health2040* research initiative project on which this dissertation is based was funded by the University of Lucerne, the Avenir Foundation, and the Foundation for Physiotherapy Science in Switzerland.

1.2.3 Dissertation Overview

Figure 1 provides an overview of the overall aim, the individual studies and reports with their specific research focuses, and the dissertation structure.

Figure 1. Overview of the objective, the studies and reports with their specific research focuses, and the structure of the dissertation

1.3 Methods

This chapter outlines the methodological foundations of the dissertation. It begins by presenting the research design and the characteristics of the study population, followed by a description of the survey instrument and the measurement of the relevant survey domains. The subsequent sections detail the procedures for data analysis and discuss ethical considerations relevant to the studies.

1.3.1 Research Design and Participants

As part of a large-scale cross-sectional study, a nationwide web-based survey was conducted among health professionals working in primary care in Switzerland. Data was collected over a period of seven months (January - July 2022). The survey targeted five core professional groups: pharmacists, physicians, medical practice assistants, nurses, and physiotherapists. These groups represent the largest segments of health professions in Switzerland, play a crucial role in primary care service delivery, and reflect its interprofessional nature.

According to national data from 2021, over 20,000 GPs, more than 5,000 pharmacists in community pharmacies, and around 10,000 physiotherapists working outside hospitals were employed in outpatient primary care (BAG, 2022a, 2022b; Merçay et al., 2021; pharmaSuisse, 2020). Nurses in outpatient settings primarily worked in home care (Lobsiger & Liechti, 2021). This broad and diverse population facilitated the exploration of professional preferences, beliefs, attitudes, and innovation capacities across these distinct groups in primary care.

Given the absence of a national database covering these professional groups comprehensively, a non-probabilistic sampling approach was employed. Following recommendations by Alvarez and VanBeselaere (2005), access to professionals was facilitated through a range of partners and media channels. These partners included professional and specialist associations, pharmacy and practice networks, interprofessional organisations as well as training and research institutions. They informed their members about the survey via newsletters, intranet platforms, member magazines or direct mailings and disseminated the survey link accordingly.

Overall, 4,063 health professionals participated in the survey, allowing for broad-based findings: 720 pharmacists, 606 physicians, 803 medical practice assistants, 643 nurses, and 1,291 physiotherapists. Although the sampling method did not ensure representativeness, the distribution of participants by sex and age closely corresponded to the demographic profile of the target population across all professional groups (Lobsiger & Liechti, 2021; Merçay et al., 2016). An overview of the study population is provided in Table 1.

The design of the study was informed by prior literature research and qualitative exploratory interviews conducted with experts from healthcare practice and the education sector of health

professionals. Specifically, research was conducted to identify which professional groups provide the majority of primary care, what challenges these health professionals in Switzerland face in their current and future work, and what possible solutions they have considered in response to these challenges.

Table 1. Comparison of the sample with the total population of health professionals

	Total	Pharmacists	Physicians	Medical practice assistants	Nurses	Physiotherapists
Total population in Switzerland, 2021 ^a	80,348 (100.0 %)	7,451 (9.3 %)	20,115 (25.0 %)	20,000 (24.9 %)	19,205 (23.9 %)	13,577 (16.9 %)
Participants in online survey	4,063 (100.0 %)	720 (17.7 %)	606 (14.9 %)	803 (19.8 %)	643 (15.8 %)	1,291 (31.8 %)
Proportion of participants in online survey in relation to total population	5.1 %	9.7 %	3.0 %	4.0 %	3.4 %	9.5 %

^aSources: Pharmacists – BAG (2022b); Physicians – BAG (2022a); Medical practice assistants – Merçay et al. (2021); Nurses – Lobsiger und Liechti (2021); Physiotherapists – Merçay et al. (2021)

1.3.2 Measurement

The survey used was a structured questionnaire specifically developed for this study and composed of close-ended questions. It consisted of a discrete choice experiment (DCE) as an experimental part and a non-experimental part. Pre-tests were carried out with survey experts and representatives of the target professional groups using the think-aloud protocol method (Ryan et al., 2009). The experimental part was additionally tested with students and professionals from the respective groups. Items that proved unclear or insufficiently comprehensive were revised accordingly. All information was self-reported, and informed consent was obtained from all participants.

The non-experimental part included questions on respondents' socio-demographic background, professional group affiliation, activities in and willingness for IPC, distribution of responsibility in clinical decision-making, professional beliefs, and willingness to work in a more health-promoting way. The short version of the individual innovativeness scale was used to measure individual innovativeness (Hurt et al., 1977; Pallister & Foxall, 1998).

The DCE was used to measure the preferences of respondents regarding the design of new models of care in primary care. This type of experiment is a methodological approach in which the respondents are placed in a specially constructed situation based on a patient case study and required to compare and evaluate different options (Auspurg & Hinz, 2014; Hainmueller et al., 2014; Viney et al., 2002). The respondents were each shown two different models of care, which consisted of four attributes and differed in the levels of these attributes. The respondents had to choose which they would prefer for patients like the case study patient in future primary care. The case study patient and description² have been developed together with health professional experts. The four attributes of the models of care were as follows:

- Professional responsible for initial contact with patients
- Professional responsible for developing and implementing the treatment plan for patients
- Type of decision-making
- Type of organisation.

In this experimental part of the questionnaire, all respondents were randomly assigned to one of two blocks. Each block consisted of seven choice sets, each consisting of two different hypothetical models of care. For each choice set, the preferred one of the two models of care presented had to be selected. A total of 1,873 people were shown the choice sets from the first block and 1,914 people were shown the choice sets from the second block. This meant that a total of 28 different hypothetical models of care were surveyed. Appendix A contains an example of a choice set in the survey.

Further information on the individual questions in the survey and on the various studies and theories that were drawn on when formulating the questions can be found in the studies I to III (chapter 2 to 4) and in the Obsan report (chapter 5).

1.3.3 Data Analysis

Discrete variables were presented with tables showing the distributions of number and percentage. The continuous variables were described by means and standard deviations. The five professional groups within the study population were compared using cross-tabulations. T-tests and chi-square tests were used to detect differences between the groups. Ordered logistic regression analyses were applied to examine associations between professional beliefs and the willingness to work more in a health-promoting way (Study I). They were also used to assess associations between the willingness to take on and relinquish more

² It is the year 2040, Mrs Widmer is 80 years old, overweight and suffers from type II diabetes mellitus, which is well controlled. She has also had recurring knee pain for several months. In recent weeks, she has experienced pain and difficulty getting going, especially in the morning. She is looking for support to alleviate her symptoms.

responsibility for decision-making and the willingness to strengthen IPC (Study II). Multiple linear regression analyses were used to evaluate associations between the profession-related characteristics and individual innovativeness (Study III). To assess the robustness of the results, sensitivity analyses were conducted in all of the three studies. Conditional logit regressions were used to analyse the DCE (McFadden & Zarembka, 1974). Data analyses were performed using R Statistical Software, Version 4.2.2 and 4.2.3 (R Core Team, 2021).

1.3.4 Ethical Considerations

The research proposal for this study has been reviewed by the Ethics Committee Northwest and Central Switzerland (Req-2022-00225). The Committee confirmed that this study did not require ethical consent under the rules of the Swiss Human Research Act (Human Research Act, 2014). An anonymous questionnaire was used, in which the name, address or other personal identifiers of the participants were not needed. Data collection and analysis were performed in accordance with the relevant guidelines and regulations.

1.4 Central Findings and Interpretations

This chapter summarises the key findings of all studies included in this dissertation and provides initial interpretations to highlight the most important insights. Detailed results can be found in the corresponding full-text articles in chapter 2, 3 and 4 and online regarding the Obsan report³ (chapter 5).

Study I revealed that health professionals, particularly non-physician health professionals, demonstrate a clear preference for health-promoting approaches over traditional biomedical models. The findings indicate that health professionals maintain a salutogenetic attitude towards their work and do not strongly support the pathogenetic biomedical model. While all professional groups showed high awareness of their role in addressing increased disease risks, significant differences emerged between professions. Non-physician health professionals advocated for a stronger preventive role in primary care, whereas physicians were less supportive of this expansion. Notably, medical practice assistants showed the most opposition to increased health promotion roles compared to other professional groups. The study demonstrated high willingness across all professions to work in more health-promoting ways, with pharmacists, nurses, and physiotherapists showing particularly strong willingness, while physicians and medical practice assistants displayed lower levels of willingness. These findings indicate that integrating health promotion may have the potential to enhance both the effectiveness of models of care and the attractiveness of primary care work.

Study II demonstrated strong willingness among health professionals to strengthen IPC and share decision-making responsibilities. The results revealed that non-physician health professions expressed high willingness to take on more responsibility for patient care decisions. Interestingly, medical practice assistants and nurses showed high willingness to relinquish responsibilities, while pharmacists and physiotherapists were less inclined to do so. Physicians displayed mixed responses, being torn between high and moderate willingness levels. A particularly significant finding was the strong statistical relationship between willingness to take on more responsibility and willingness to strengthen IPC. These findings indicate that sharing responsibility between professional groups, supported by targeted education programmes, could enhance IPC, optimise coordination of care, reduce errors and ultimately increase the attractiveness of working in primary care.

Study III revealed that non-physician health professionals, particularly those with advanced education and leadership roles, demonstrate higher levels of individual innovativeness compared to physicians. Nurses, physiotherapists, and pharmacists showed particularly high levels of individual innovativeness. The study identified several factors associated with higher

³ https://www.obsan.admin.ch/sites/default/files/2023-06/Obsan_06_2023_BERICHT.pdf (accessed 29 June, 2025)

degrees of innovativeness: advanced professional education versus basic professional education, greater professional experience, and leadership responsibilities among employed individuals. These findings suggest that non-physician health professionals may be better positioned than physicians to address current and future primary care challenges. The study indicates that non-physician health professionals could be better equipped than physicians to meet the challenges in current and future primary care. Recognizing and utilizing this innovation capacity while making professionals feel valued for their contributions could significantly enhance the attractiveness of primary care work.

The Obsan report examined professional preferences for future primary care through a case study of patients with both chronic and acute complaints. The findings revealed that professionals from all groups generally favoured models of care where their own profession takes responsibility for first contact and treatment planning. However, pharmacists were consistently less favoured by other professions for these roles, despite pharmacists themselves believing they could assume such responsibilities for the case study patient. The report demonstrated that pharmacists, nurses, and physiotherapists particularly desire models of care that deviate from the current status quo, preferring new models where their professions assume greater responsibility and tasks compared to today's GP-centred approach. Significantly, all professional groups favoured collective decision-making models for future care. Regarding organisational preferences, individual practices were least favoured across all groups, with pharmacists uniquely preferring health centres while other professions favoured healthcare networks. These preferences suggest that moving away from GP-centred models toward more collaborative approaches could increase primary care work attractiveness and better utilise diverse professional expertise.

1.5 Discussion

This dissertation presents the first studies to systematically examine the attitudes and preferences of the five largest groups of health professionals in Swiss primary care regarding new models of care. Its overarching aim is to generate empirical evidence to support the design of innovative and sustainable models of care, based on the attitudes and preferences of health professionals. The findings offer valuable insights for new primary care model development, highlighting the relevance of health promotion, IPC, the distribution of responsibilities, and the innovation capacity of health professionals. The results show that health professionals – especially those in non-physician roles – are willing to engage in health promotion, take on greater responsibility, collaborate on an interprofessional level, and contribute to innovation. Despite profession-specific preferences and limited trust in the competencies of other professional groups, health professionals across all five professions express a clear preference for new models of primary care that are interprofessional, feature shared decision-making processes, and move away from the traditional single-handed practice towards more collaborative structures such as health centres and health networks. Non-physician health professionals are open to assuming greater responsibility and prefer models of care that go beyond the traditional GP-centred structure. These findings provide strong empirical support for the design of new models of primary care that are based on the attitudes and preferences of health professionals, team-oriented, and inclusive of all health professions.

The following chapter discusses and further interprets these findings. The first part compares the findings with previous literature on attitudes and preferences of health professionals, while the second part compares them with the results of the *Health2040 research initiative* on the general population in Switzerland. This is followed by a section that places the findings within relevant theoretical frameworks to better understand how attitudes and preferences may be translated into practice. The chapter concludes with a discussion of the strengths and limitations of this dissertation.

1.5.1 Comparison with Previous Research on Health Professionals

In line with previous studies, this dissertation found that health professionals in primary care value health promotion activities and are willing to work more in a health-promoting way (Keyworth et al., 2019). These professional beliefs have been confirmed by previous researchers as facilitating factors for implementing and sustaining health promoting activities during day-to-day work in healthcare (Keyworth et al., 2020; Strid et al., 2023; van der Heiden et al., 2022). The findings regarding physicians' lower willingness to undertake additional work in health promotion have also been confirmed in previous research. Calderón et al. (2011) report that GPs want to focus on their priority tasks in treating their patients, with health promotion often considered secondary and not carried out due to time constraints. Nutbeam

et al. (2021) emphasise that the shift from disease to risk factors is also important in terms of global health in order to identify pathways for the application of health promotion strategies. The study of the professional beliefs of health professionals in Switzerland included in this dissertation makes an important contribution to preparing for this shift.

The results of the studies included in this dissertation reveal discrepancies between the self-perception and external perception of health professionals. There appears to be a clear gap between what professional groups believe they are capable of and what others believe they are capable of. This is particularly evident among pharmacists, who see themselves as competent in initial contact and treatment planning but are not considered to be ideal for this role by other professional groups. On the one hand, this points to a need for communication and education about the actual competencies of different professional groups among health professionals. This need for education and role clarification, particularly with regard to pharmacists working in primary care, has been confirmed by several studies (Claire et al., 2022; Kennie-Kaulbach et al., 2012). On the other hand, the added value of employing pharmacists in primary care is emphasised, particularly in medication therapy management and disease-focused management of diabetes, which partly corresponds to the case study patient from the experimental study (Truong et al., 2017).

Foster et al. (2016) highlight the importance of innovative health professionals in primary care. They emphasise that local, innovative health professionals, for example, help to implement innovations in care and encourage those involved to provide support. Abby et al. (2019) argue that professionalism in primary care also means reflecting on complex situations in care and creating positive change (Anders Ericsson, 2008). Ultimately, the commitment of professionals to their work, i.e. their willingness, ability and opportunity to be innovative, is the key to innovation (Avby et al., 2019).

The results of the study on the pronounced innovativeness of health professionals thus clearly show that the health professionals surveyed have the potential to implement innovations in care, promote support for innovations in their environment, and promote professionalism in primary care.

Previous research findings confirm the preferences of non-physician health professionals for models of care that are not GP-centred. A study in the Netherlands examined the 'physicians in the lead' (PIL) strategy, that involves physicians in organisational processes, holding them accountable for the quality and efficiency of their department's care delivery (Malik et al., 2018). This strategy is based on the belief that physicians deliver effective, efficient and cost-effective healthcare and have the power to lead healthcare reforms (Porter & Teisberg, 2007). It was found that the PIL strategy does not adequately support the holistic care approach that is increasingly demanded by patients (Malik et al., 2018). This was particularly due to the

biomedical focus, which is described in the first study of this dissertation as a pathogenetic attitude. Instead of the PIL strategy, Malik et al. (2018) proposed a 'team in the lead' strategy to strengthen integrated care and teamwork. This strategy should take into account the fact that different health professions are complementary to each other. In view of the findings of the second study of this dissertation regarding the willingness of health professionals to strengthen IPC, redistribute responsibilities and the preferences of non-physician health professionals to take on more responsibility for first contact and treatment planning, this 'team in the lead' strategy also appears to be a promising way of making the work of health professionals in future primary care more attractive in the Swiss context.

Further parallels between the findings of previous studies and those of this dissertation can be found in the results reported by Leach et al. (2018). The health professionals surveyed expressed positive attitudes towards integrated care and supported the provision of a broad range of support and health services for individuals with chronic conditions, based on triage by non-physician health professionals. These findings may reflect salutogenic professional beliefs and a strong willingness among respondents to engage in health promotion. Moreover, they suggest that – similar to the participants in the studies included in this dissertation – the respondents support an expanded role of non-physician health professionals in first contact care and treatment planning.

Krczal (2017) also emphasised the importance of involving the healthcare workforce in the planning of new models of care. Her study drew similar conclusions to this dissertation: Physicians emerged as the group most reluctant to embrace changes towards integrated models of care. For non-physician health professionals, integrated models of care were particularly attractive as a way of expanding their areas of responsibility and taking on more challenging tasks with stronger social relationships, e.g. through IPC. Although the study included only a sample of 267 health professionals, it encompassed physicians, nurses, and physiotherapists. While pharmacists and medical practice assistants were not surveyed, the sample composition is nevertheless similar to that of the studies conducted as part of this dissertation.

The findings of Gilles et al. (2025) and those of this dissertation are complementary in several respects. The frustration expressed by participants in the *Swiss Cohort of Healthcare Professionals and Informal Caregivers* survey (Gilles et al., 2025; Peytremann-Bridevaux et al., 2024) regarding their limited influence on health policy, as well as their references to structural inefficiencies in the current system, may help to explain the observed preferences for increased responsibility and shared decision-making – and, by extension, for greater influence in shaping care. Based on their findings, Gilles et al. (2025) formulate recommendations that are also aligned with the results of this dissertation: strategies to strengthen workforce retention do not require profession-specific solutions. Instead, clusters

of professionals should be identified who share characteristics such as career development patterns, so that tailored measures can be developed to enhance job attractiveness across these clusters.

In research on employer attractiveness in healthcare, little attention has been paid to the preferences of health professionals regarding the design of new models of care. Instead, the focus has been on factors such as working environment, team spirit, sincerity, fair leadership, reliable work schedules and reliable colleagues, which nursing professionals have rated as attractive (Koch-Rogge & Westermann, 2021). Social values with factors such as team cohesion and social responsibility have less influence on employer attractiveness (Heide et al., 2024). This could contradict the study results of this dissertation, although interpretation is difficult due to the lack of comparability between the study questions. Research on employer attractiveness appears to focus more on the characteristics of the employer than on the actual area of activity and responsibility, which is of greater interest to the studies of this dissertation on the design of new models of care.

1.5.2 Comparison with Health2040-Research on General Population

As outlined above, this dissertation is embedded within the *Health2040* research initiative. The following section therefore compares the findings of the studies included in this dissertation with those of other studies conducted within the *Health2040* framework.

A comparison of the study results published in the Obsan report with the results of the survey of the general population in Switzerland (Kaufmann et al., 2021) reveals both remarkable convergences and fundamental discrepancies between health professionals' preferences and those of the general population regarding new models of care in primary care.

The first significant area of tension is the preference for continuity versus collectivity. While the general population prefers models of care that ensure continuity of treatment by the same professional, i.e. the GP, and specifically wishes this professional to be familiar with their medical history, the surveyed health professionals primarily focus on collective decision-making models within interprofessional teams. These different emphases point to a fundamental tension: the population prefers a continuous single point of contact, while professionals emphasise the advantages of team-based approaches.

As a second area of tension, the distribution of roles and professional group acceptance has been identified. The differences are particularly pronounced in the evaluation of different professional groups. While the population primarily prefers physicians as first contact, it also shows an openness toward nurses. In contrast, each surveyed professional group preferred itself for first contact and treatment planning, while pharmacists consistently received little acceptance from other professions for these roles. This discrepancy between the population's

relative openness and the interprofessional competition among health professionals could represent a significant barrier to implementing new and innovative models of care.

The third central difference lies in the fundamental attitude toward change. The population survey identified a pronounced *status quo bias* – respondents envision future primary care in many respects very similarly to today's system of care delivery. In contrast, health professionals, particularly non-physician health professionals such as nurses, physiotherapists, and pharmacists, express a strong desire to move away from the current physician-centred system and strive for greater responsibility and an expanded scope of practice.

Despite the discrepancies, important convergences emerge. Both groups seem to prefer integrated models of care: health professionals reject single practices and favour health centres or networks, while the population values coordination and collaboration between healthcare providers. Moreover, both sides consider involvement in decision-making processes important, albeit with different emphases – the population desires patient participation, while professionals prefer collective professional decisions.

These findings illustrate the complexity of transforming models of primary care. While health professionals stand ready as potential drivers of change, the population's preference for familiar structures requires careful change management strategies. A particularly critical element appears to be the need to develop continuity concepts that enable both the desired personal relationship between patient and health professional, and the professionally preferred IPC with different professionals responsible for first contact and treatment planning.

The tensions identified between the self-perception and external perception of different professional groups also underscore the importance of interprofessional dialogue and role clarification. Action plans, such as the aforementioned *Gesundheitsnetz für alle – pour tous – per tutti (Health Network for All)* (Balthasar et al., 2024), and successful reforms in the healthcare system must take into account both the ambitions of healthcare professionals and the expectations of the population and integrate them into a coherent model that makes optimal use of professional expertise while respecting patient preferences.

1.5.3 Theoretical Perspectives on Implementing Attitudes and Preferences

The findings of this dissertation show that positive attitudes and preferences for health promotion, IPC, and shared responsibility are widespread among the health professionals surveyed – particularly among those in non-physician roles. However, translating these preferences into everyday professional practice is dependent on behavioural and contextual factors. The *COM-B model* conceptualises behaviour (B) as a function of capability (C), opportunity (O), and motivation (M) (Michie et al., 2011; West & Michie, 2020), providing a framework to understand why positive attitudes do not automatically lead to behavioural

change. Within this model, the preferences expressed by health professionals can be interpreted primarily as indicators of motivation. Without sufficient capability (e.g. skills, knowledge, confidence) or opportunity (e.g. time, resources, organisational support), motivation alone may be insufficient to bring about change in primary care practice through new models of care.

The *Consolidated Framework for Implementation Research* (CFIR) likewise emphasises that the implementation of new models of care is shaped by multiple influencing factors, including organisational culture, leadership engagement, compatibility with existing workflows (inner setting), and political and financial frameworks (outer setting) (Damschroder et al., 2022; Safaeinili et al., 2019). From this perspective, attitudes and preferences can be understood as enabling conditions that interact with other dimensions of implementation. For example, a preference for innovative organisational forms, such as regional health networks, will only be realised in practice if external regulations permit such models and participating health professionals are supported with appropriate resources.

The attitudes and preferences identified in this dissertation can also be interpreted through the lens of the *Normalisation Process Theory*. This theory focuses on the social processes by which new practices become embedded in routine work and comprises four core constructs: coherence (making sense of the change), cognitive participation (engagement and commitment), collective action (the work undertaken to enact the change), and reflexive monitoring (appraisal and adaptation) (Huddlestone et al., 2020; Murray et al., 2010). The positive attitudes towards health promotion and shared responsibility observed in this study suggest that coherence and cognitive participation are relatively high within the professional groups surveyed. However, positive attitudes alone do not guarantee successful collective action, which may be constrained by structural barriers such as a lack of time and training or inadequate reimbursement mechanisms. Reflexive monitoring mechanisms – such as structured feedback loops and outcome evaluations – are crucial to ensure that newly implemented models remain aligned with professional values and achieve their intended benefits.

Overall, these theoretical perspectives suggest that attitudes and preferences are a valuable starting point for understanding the readiness of health professionals to change. To assess the successful transfer of attitudes and preferences into practice, future research should interpret them in conjunction with contextual and behavioural determinants.

1.5.4 Strengths and Limitations

This dissertation demonstrates several key methodological and conceptual strengths that contribute to its robustness and significance within the field of health services research.

The participation of over 4,000 health professionals in this survey represents a substantial achievement in health services research, providing a broad empirical foundation for the findings. Extensive measures were implemented to distribute the survey and motivate the broadest possible participation of health professionals in the study. While the recruitment approach and probability sampling method did not allow for a fully representative sample of the target population, the gender and age distribution across all professional groups within the sample closely mirrors that of the target populations. The large sample size enables robust statistical analyses. The scale of participation is particularly noteworthy given the challenges typically associated with engaging health professionals in research activities, and it establishes a sound empirical base that distinguishes this study from comparable research with smaller sample sizes. Apart from an ongoing survey within the *Swiss Cohort of Healthcare Professionals and Informal Caregivers* (Gilles et al., 2025; Peytremann-Bridevaux et al., 2024; Roth, Gilles, et al., 2024; Roth, Le Saux, et al., 2024), no other study is known to have included such a wide range of professional groups and such a high number of participants across Switzerland.

A significant strength lies in the systematic approach to questionnaire development, where existing validated instruments were utilised wherever possible to ensure comparability with previous studies and maintain methodological rigour. Questions addressing willingness to take on more responsibility and focus on health promotion were based on the validated work of Johansson et al. (2010). Similarly, the assessment of prerequisites and framework conditions for assuming responsibility drew upon Johansson et al.'s established questionnaire. For measuring individual innovativeness, the study employed a shortened and validated version of a questionnaire with extensive research heritage (Hurt et al., 1977; Pallister & Foxall, 1998). This systematic reliance on validated instruments strengthens the study's methodological foundation and facilitates meaningful comparisons with existing literature.

The study's novelty represents a considerable strength, as the specific research questions, analytical approaches, and methodological combinations employed have not been previously explored in this configuration. The national cross-sectional survey design encompassing five distinct professional groups provides an unprecedented comprehensive view of interprofessional perspectives within the Swiss healthcare system. The integration of a DCE methodology within this specific research context and with these particular objectives represents a methodological innovation that advances the field's analytical capabilities. This combination of traditional survey methods with advanced choice modelling techniques offers new insights into health professionals' preferences and decision-making processes.

The study's quantitative approach provides distinct advantages within the broader research landscape, offering the precision and statistical power necessary to identify patterns and relationships across large populations of health professionals. This methodological positioning

allows for the generation of findings that can inform evidence-based policy decisions and contribute to the development of robust theoretical frameworks in healthcare delivery research.

The study's focus on new models of care represents a particularly timely contribution to health services research, as the exploration of innovative care delivery approaches is currently at the forefront of healthcare policy discussions across many countries (Gordon et al., 2020; Mutsekwa et al., 2024; Roberts et al., 2023). In Switzerland specifically, this research aligns directly with ongoing policy initiatives, as evidenced by the Federal Office of Public Health's efforts regarding the *Primary Care Agenda* (BAG, 2025b). This contemporaneous policy focus underscores the immediate relevance of the study's findings and positions the research to inform current policy debates and implementation strategies.

The research demonstrates exceptional strength in its direct application to healthcare policy and practice. The findings served as the empirical foundation for developing the action plan *Gesundheitsnetz für alle – pour tous – per tutti (Health Network for All)*, which is aimed at designing sustainable models of care for Switzerland's future healthcare needs (Balthasar et al., 2024). This knowledge translation occurred through a collaborative co-creation process involving stakeholders from the social and health sectors as well as civil society representatives. This participatory approach to implementing research findings exemplifies best practices in knowledge mobilisation and ensures that the study's contributions extend beyond academic discourse to influence real-world healthcare delivery improvements.

Despite its considerable strengths, this research is subject to several important limitations that must be acknowledged and considered when interpreting the findings.

The results are not statistically representative in the strict sense, which constitutes a significant methodological limitation. The absence of a national database of all health professionals necessitated a bottom-up approach, requiring the recruitment of members from professional associations, specialist organisations, and other healthcare organisations. Whilst pragmatic given the constraints, the chosen sampling strategy may have contributed to a different distribution of professional groups in the sample compared to the total population of health professionals in Switzerland (Table 1). The sampling strategy may introduce selection bias and limit the generalisability of findings to the broader population of health professionals in Switzerland.

The extensive scope of the questionnaire used for the studies of this dissertation presents another limitation, with participation requiring considerable time investment (median completion time: 17.4 minutes). This substantial response burden resulted in approximately one-fifth of participants failing to complete all questions, potentially introducing systematic bias through differential completion patterns (Bethlehem, 2010; Bogner & Landrock, 2016). The incomplete responses may particularly affect the robustness of analyses requiring complete

data sets and could influence the interpretation of preferences across different professional groups (Galesic & Bosnjak, 2009; Groves et al., 2004).

Despite the potential for discussing new role distributions, the study's reliance on preferences derived from a single patient case study represents a significant limitation. Although this case study patient was carefully and realistically selected and developed together with health professional experts, it is reasonable to suspect that alternative patient case studies might have yielded different results. The case was deliberately designed to allow all five professional groups to contribute from their respective expertise, and the results suggest that professionals could accurately assess their competencies, as evidenced by their rating of their own professional roles as important. This suggests that comparable case examples would likely produce similar results. However, case examples featuring conditions clearly attributable to specific professions (such as emergency treatments or medication counselling) would likely result in markedly different role attributions across professional groups.

Fundamentally, eliciting preferences regarding future scenarios presents inherent methodological challenges. Participants' conceptions of future primary care are heavily influenced by the current system, which must be considered when interpreting results. This limitation is inherent in all prognostic studies, where uncertainty exists regarding whether stated assumptions will prove accurate in future contexts (Bachleitner et al., 2016). The status quo likely influenced responses, though given that many collaborative models of care are not yet widely established, this influence on participants' responses is presumably limited.

The methodological limitations identified in this study reveal important boundaries inherent in large-scale cross-sectional survey research within healthcare settings. The tension between achieving statistical representativeness and practical feasibility demonstrates the ongoing challenges in health services research, particularly when investigating interprofessional perspectives. The substantial response burden required for comprehensive data collection conflicts with health professionals' time constraints, whilst the reliance on single case scenarios for preference elicitation, though methodologically necessary, limits the breadth of insights that can be generated. These methodological boundaries are not merely technical limitations but reflect fundamental challenges in capturing the complexity of healthcare delivery preferences through quantitative methods. The experience gained from navigating these constraints provides a foundation for future research designs that might better balance comprehensiveness with feasibility, potentially through mixed-methods approaches or innovative sampling strategies that could address the representativeness challenges whilst maintaining the analytical power demonstrated by this study's large sample size.

1.6 Implications

The following chapter discusses the implications of the dissertation's findings. First, it explores the different levels at which the models of care preferred by health professionals may help address current challenges and megatrends in healthcare. This is followed by a reflection on how this dissertation contributes to the policy debate on the design of new models of care. Finally, implications for the education of health professionals, for healthcare practice, and for future research are outlined.

1.6.1 Addressing Challenges and Megatrends in Healthcare

The findings of this dissertation offer specific implications for addressing current challenges and megatrends that will shape society and the healthcare system in Switzerland in the future. Health professionals not only recognise the need for change, but also express clear preferences for models of care that could alleviate structural weaknesses in the existing GP-centred system. Key levers for strengthening the system's sustainability include redistributing responsibilities, promoting health, enhancing IPC, adopting innovative organisational forms and using the innovative capacity of non-physician health professionals.

Redistributing responsibilities could reduce the burden on GPs. The current GP-centred model concentrates responsibility for first contact and treatment planning on a single professional group. However, non-physician health professionals demonstrate high willingness to take on more responsibility for decision-making in patient care. This willingness to assume responsibility enables a redistribution of workload from a centralised to a decentralised system. When pharmacists, nurses, and physiotherapists take on more tasks in first contact care and treatment planning, pressure on GP care is systematically reduced. This is particularly relevant given demographic change and the increasing demand for health services.

A further lever lies in strengthening health promotion. Non-physician professionals show a clear preference for health-promoting approaches over biomedical ones. This salutogenetic attitude contributes to long-term prevention, allowing for earlier identification of chronic conditions and reducing the need for resource-intensive curative interventions. The higher willingness of pharmacists, nurses, and physiotherapists to work in more health-promoting ways thus creates a preventive layer that eases the burden on the curative system.

The findings also underscore the role of IPC in increasing efficiency. The strong willingness of all professional groups to strengthen IPC and collective decision-making leads to optimised resource utilisation. Instead of individual professionals attempting to cover all aspects of patient care, IPC enables competency-based task sharing. Each professional group can contribute their specific strengths, while the individual innovativeness of non-physician health professionals brings new solution approaches into care. This specialisation and collaboration

might lead to more efficient treatment processes and might reduce redundancies in the healthcare system.

The preference for health networks and health centres over individual practices might also create structural relief on multiple levels. Healthcare networks enable better distribution of patient flows, shared infrastructure, and collegial support. This reduces the workload of individual professionals and increases overall capacity, thereby preventing bottlenecks in primary care. The rejection of individual practice as a future model of care by all professional groups demonstrates awareness of the limitations of isolated care structures.

The higher individual innovativeness of non-physician health professionals, particularly among nurses, physiotherapists, and pharmacists, contributes to systemic resilience, e.g. by enabling primary care to respond to rising rates of chronic diseases with novel approaches to patient education and self-management, and to integrate digital tools that enhance efficiency and access. Innovation in healthcare fosters new workflows, treatment approaches, and service models. By granting these professionals more autonomy and decision-making power within preferred models of care, their innovative capacity can be more effectively harnessed.

The findings of this dissertation also reveal that health professionals in Swiss primary care are attitudinally well prepared to address key healthcare megatrends. Megatrends are understood as developments that are global in scope, long-term in duration, and complex in nature (Deml et al., 2022; Zukunftsinstitut, 2025). These include: socio-demographic shifts, broadening definitions of health and patients, the infodemic coupled with patient empowerment, digitalisation in healthcare, and changes in care and models of care (Deml et al., 2022).

Regarding *socio-demographic shifts*, health professionals demonstrate considerable readiness to adapt to demographic changes through their willingness to strengthen IPC and preference to work in health centres and networks. This aligns well with the need for coordinated models of care addressing ageing populations and urbanisation patterns (Carron et al., 2023; GDK & BAG, 2012; Giger & De Geest, 2008). The openness of non-physician health professionals to assume greater responsibility is particularly relevant given potential physician shortages (Bolliger et al., 2016; Kraft et al., 2016).

For *broadening health definitions*, the findings reveal strong support for health promotion activities, indicating preparedness for expanded conceptualisations of health beyond traditional medical treatment such as salutogenetic instead of pathogenetic approaches to care (Pelikan, 2017).

While *patient empowerment* and *digitalisation* were not explicitly examined, health professionals' individual innovativeness and openness to innovative models of care suggest foundational readiness for digital transformation. The health professionals' preference for collaborative structures may facilitate digital health solutions requiring coordinated data

approaches. Health professionals' commitment to shared decision-making is crucial for navigating contexts where patients arrive with varying health information quality. Their collaborative care preferences suggest readiness to guide patients through complex information landscapes, though limited interprofessional trust may hinder effective responses.

The findings most directly address *changes in models of care*, with clear evidence that health professionals across all professions prefer innovative models of care. Their move from traditional single-handed practice toward interprofessional, team-oriented approaches aligns with care model evolution trends.

Overall, health professionals in Swiss primary care possess many attitudinal foundations necessary to address healthcare megatrends effectively. Their preference for collaborative, team-based models and their individual innovativeness positions them well for demographic and technological challenges. However, profession-specific preferences and interprofessional trust limitations may require targeted interventions to fully realise their potential in responding to these megatrends.

1.6.2 Contribution to the Political Debate

Political recommendations can be derived from the results of the studies conducted. The most important ones are described in the Policy Brief⁴ included in this dissertation (chapter 5). The full publication can be found online.

Empowering Non-Physician Health Professionals

The findings reveal substantial untapped potential amongst non-physician health professionals that remains underutilised in the current GP-centred care system. This situation creates frustration amongst these professionals, as their skills and competencies are not adequately recognised or employed in their daily work. Instead, they are often confined to tasks that highlight their limited scope of practice rather than leveraging their full capabilities. This underutilisation not only limits the quality of healthcare provision but also contributes to workforce shortages by perpetuating a cycle of professional dissatisfaction.

Policymakers should empower non-physician health professionals by allowing them to take on responsibility for first contact and developing treatment plans through pilot projects implemented by insurers and service providers. This approach would enable the specification of opportunities and limits within these expanded roles. Evidence indicates that non-physician health professionals such as pharmacists and nurses are well positioned to assume substantially expanded roles in supporting physicians in primary care in response to changing healthcare demands. These roles may include direct patient care, independent prescribing, counselling, and education, delivered with comparable quality of care (Leong et al., 2021).

⁴ https://www.slhs.ch/media/yzjq3vj/policy-brief_sophie-brandt.pdf (accessed 29 June, 2025)

Task sharing and task shifting are particularly suitable for improving teamwork, efficiency, and quality of healthcare provision. Both forms of task management benefit from well-trained professionals and lead to expanded care possibilities. Treatment and care are better adapted to context, organisational cultures, and the sociocultural circumstances of patients. Appropriate planning, sufficient resources, education and continuing professional development, training, and transparency are essential. To achieve these goals, corresponding structures such as health regions, care and navigation models, and transparent financing systems are required, along with further measures and research. The Triple Aims of Healthcare – improving individual experiences with care, improving population health, and reducing per capita costs of population care – as well as patient needs can be guiding principles (Zumstein-Shaha et al., 2024).

Strengthening Professional Roles

The results show that strengthening non-physician health professionals is central to the design of new models in primary care in order to meet the preferences of these professional groups and make their work attractive. In physiotherapy, the example of direct access demonstrates that it is a safe, cost-effective, and reliable model for triage and management, leading to higher patient satisfaction compared with the traditional medical model (Gallotti et al., 2023). By drawing on its evidence-based approaches, physiotherapy could contribute to addressing some of the challenges facing the Swiss healthcare system.

Another example of strengthening non-physician health professionals could be the involvement of APNs. In the canton of Bern, the Health and Social Welfare Committee of the Grand Council has expressed support for APNs taking on more tasks from GPs, although this would require legal changes at the federal level. (Gesundheits- und Sozialkommission des Grossen Rates, 2025). To ensure that APNs can be rolled out as quickly as possible in the canton of Bern once federal legal obstacles have been overcome, the cantonal government should examine various measures to accelerate the process. The Health and Social Welfare Commission calls for planning declarations to establish an advisory centre for medical practices and municipalities interested in the APN model, as well as a programme to promote APN training qualifications. Furthermore, a legal basis should be created to allow APNs in the canton of Bern to take on low-level tasks from GPs, such as prescribing certain drug therapies (Gesundheits- und Sozialkommission des Grossen Rates, 2025).

The academisation of nursing and physiotherapy professions, along with expanded continuing education in all areas of pharmacy and medical practice assistance, supports the strengthening of non-physician professions. This promotes professional and communicative competencies, decision-making and leadership skills, and could lead to rising expectations and demands on professional roles.

Improving Healthcare Service Organisation

The findings of this dissertation point to important directions for strengthening the organisation of healthcare services in response to increasing care needs. Surveyed health professionals expressed a clear willingness to engage in health promotion and to assume broader responsibilities in patient care. This is particularly relevant for the management of chronic conditions, many of which can be addressed effectively and at substantially lower cost within primary care rather than through inpatient treatment (Djalali et al., 2015; Starfield et al., 2005). The growing prevalence of chronic diseases highlights the need for a dual strategy that prioritises prevention and rehabilitation (Polanco et al., 2025). In line with the attitudes observed in this dissertation, preventive measures such as promoting healthy nutrition and physical activity from an early age can be advanced through IPC and patient counselling, representing cost-effective approaches to reducing the burden of NCDs (Probst-Hensch et al., 2011). At the same time, integrating rehabilitation more systematically into routine care for individuals living with chronic conditions reflects both professional preferences and system-level necessity (Polanco et al., 2025). Rehabilitation not only supports patients in regaining independence and quality of life, but also prevents complications that may otherwise result in avoidable hospital admissions (Bunyan et al., 2016).

In this context, the *Primary Care Agenda* (BAG, 2025b) seeks to contribute to a sustainable care system. Its measures include the further development and implementation of innovative models of care, the evolution of professional roles, and the exploitation of opportunities created by digital transformation. Drawing on evidence from existing models as examples of good practice can further support this development. Taken together, these findings suggest that aligning service organisation with the demonstrated willingness of health professionals to expand their roles, while drawing on national strategies such as the *Primary Care Agenda*, could contribute to more effective and sustainable models of care.

Fostering Interprofessional Collaboration, Health Promotion and Innovation

Policymakers should foster IPC by creating more opportunities for IPC, supporting health networks and health centres as organisational types of primary care, and supporting local engagement of cantons to ensure primary care service provision in rural areas. The introduction of the Electronic Patient Record (EPD) could serve as a tool to promote IPC, responsibility sharing, and health promotion in primary care.

The professionals' willingness to work more in a health-promoting way should be leveraged by implementing targeted interventions. Policymakers should use the high innovativeness of health professionals by ensuring easy access to funding for professionals to implement innovative ideas. Additionally, pharmacists' interests in playing a more active role in future primary care should be utilised by increasing health professionals' trust in their competencies.

1.6.3 Implications for Education and Practice

The findings of this dissertation have implications beyond policy development, extending to educational institutions and healthcare practice settings. These stakeholders play crucial roles in translating the identified preferences of health professionals into tangible improvements in primary care delivery.

Educational Implications

Educational institutions must adapt their curricula and training approaches to prepare health professionals for the collaborative, responsibility-sharing models they have indicated a preference for. Interprofessional education should become standard practice across all health professional programmes, enabling students to develop the collaborative skills and mutual understanding necessary for effective teamwork (Grand-Guillaume-Perrenoud et al., 2025). This foundational training is essential for breaking down professional silos that currently limit the full utilisation of each profession's capabilities.

Training programmes for non-physician health professionals must incorporate modules focused on responsibility-taking and decision-making competencies. This includes developing clinical reasoning skills, leadership capabilities, and the confidence to assume expanded roles within primary care teams. Such preparation is particularly important given the demonstrated willingness of these professionals to take on greater responsibilities.

Educational institutions should promote and utilise the innovation capabilities evident amongst health professionals, particularly non-physician professionals. This involves fostering entrepreneurial thinking, encouraging creative problem-solving approaches, and providing platforms for students to develop and test innovative care delivery methods. Additionally, educational programmes must cultivate openness to new models of care, preparing graduates to adapt to evolving healthcare environments rather than adhering rigidly to traditional practice patterns.

Importantly, physician and medical practice assistant training programmes should also incorporate guidance toward health-promoting work, ensuring that all members of primary care teams are equipped to contribute to preventive and salutogenetic approaches to care.

Practice Implications

Healthcare practice settings must actively utilise and expand opportunities for IPC. This requires creating organisational structures that facilitate communication, shared decision-making, and coordinated care delivery. Practice managers and healthcare leaders must recognise that effective IPC extends beyond mere co-location of professionals to encompass genuine collaboration in patient care decisions.

Practices should maintain openness to innovations, particularly regarding responsibility distribution and new care delivery approaches. This involves establishing mechanisms for piloting new models, evaluating their effectiveness, and scaling successful innovations. The demonstrated individual innovativeness of health professionals, particularly among non-physician groups, represents a valuable resource that practices should actively harness.

Healthcare settings must also utilise and expand opportunities for health promotion activities. Given the strong preference for health-promoting approaches among non-physician health professionals, practices should develop systems that enable these professionals to engage meaningfully in preventive care, patient education, and community health initiatives.

1.6.4 Implications for Further Research

Future research must address several critical areas to support the translation of health professional preferences into effective models of care. Investigation of the prerequisites for models including task shifting and task sharing is essential. A particularly important research question emerges from the apparent discrepancy between survey responses and practical implementation: What prerequisites must be fulfilled for physicians to be willing in reality (not just in surveys) to delegate responsibility in decision-making in primary care for their patients? The surprising finding that physicians showed high willingness to delegate responsibility in surveys contrasts with contrary experiences observed in practice, suggesting that significant barriers to implementation exist that require systematic investigation. Building on the COM-B framework (Michie et al., 2011), studies could examine which capability, opportunity, and motivation factors most strongly facilitate or hinder such delegation in practice. Longitudinal designs could, for example, explore whether initial positive attitudes towards health promotion or shared responsibility are more likely to result in behavioural change when capability and opportunity are deliberately strengthened through training, resource allocation, or regulatory reform.

There is limited evidence for the effectiveness and quality of healthcare in new models of primary care, representing a critical research gap. Current tariff structures are oriented toward disease treatment and care of the ill, typically reflecting only direct patient work. The lack of financing for new models of care with innovative approaches or for health promotion is emphasised by many studies (Herzlinger, 2006; Kelley et al., 2020; Koleva-Kolarova et al., 2022; Rowthorn et al., 2016; Rubio-Valera et al., 2014). Political resistance exists against expanding health professionals' service catalogues due to concerns about healthcare costs and volume expansion. Future research should therefore focus on investigating the effectiveness, appropriateness, and economic efficiency of strengthening the involvement of health professionals in first contact care, treatment planning, health promotion, and IPC in primary care, with particular attention to the role of non-physician health professionals. The

successful example of fall prevention services, where physiotherapists will be able to provide and bill for fall prevention beyond their traditional therapy role (Medinside, 2025; Physioswiss, 2025), could serve as a model for expanding other health promotion services.

From an implementation science perspective, future studies could also investigate which organisational and policy-level determinants are most critical for translating attitudes and preferences into practice. Mixed-methods research could examine the interplay between individual-level motivation and systemic factors such as reimbursement models, regulatory frameworks, and interprofessional care structures. For example, a sequential explanatory design could combine a nationwide survey on health professionals' willingness to assume new roles with subsequent focus groups or interviews that explore how reimbursement schemes, legal frameworks, and workplace cultures influence their actual readiness to adopt such roles.

Another research priority is to clarify the role of attitudes and preferences both in the broader process of healthcare innovation and in the process of transferring new models of care into routine practice. This includes examining whether they are best understood as precursors to innovation and the development of new models of care, or as indicators of ongoing engagement that should be monitored and supported throughout the implementation process. Embedding the assessment of attitudes and preferences in pilot projects and implementation studies could help to determine whether they shift in parallel with changes in practice, and whether such shifts contribute to the sustainability and normalisation of new models of care.

Research must also address coordination and integration challenges: How can integrated care succeed when the GP is no longer solely responsible for first contact and the development and implementation of treatment plans, but rather non-physician health professionals (possibly from different professional groups) take on these roles? This question is fundamental to understanding how to maintain care continuity and quality whilst expanding professional roles.

Finally, research should investigate how preferences of the population and preferences of health professionals can be combined into viable models of primary care. Different population groups have different preferences, with the group having the highest treatment costs (older, multimorbid persons) simultaneously preferring an expensive model of care (GP-centred, continuous contact person, low price sensitivity) (Föhn, 2025). Understanding how to encourage this influential group to support new innovative models is crucial for creating the political momentum necessary for system transformation. Complementary to this, patient-reported outcomes and experiences should be systematically integrated into evaluations of new models of care. Such evidence would help determine whether changes in professional roles and care structures align not only with professional preferences but also with the needs and preferences of patients themselves.

1.7 Conclusion

This dissertation presents the first systematic examination of attitudes and preferences regarding new models of care among the five largest health professional groups in Swiss primary care. By emphasising the perspectives and innovative capacity of health professionals, it contributes empirical evidence essential for designing models of care that align closely to the expectations and capacities of care providers. Such models have the potential not only to mitigate systemic challenges, including workforce shortages and growing complexity, but also to enhance care quality, professional satisfaction, and the attractiveness of careers in primary care.

The findings indicate that health professionals – particularly those in non-physician roles – have a clear preference for interprofessional models characterised by shared decision-making and collaborative organisational forms, such as health centres and networks. Non-physician professionals express substantial willingness to assume increased responsibilities in patient care and also demonstrate considerable willingness to engage in health promotion activities.

Despite profession-specific differences and concerns regarding cross-professional competencies, the results reveal a shared interest in moving away from traditional GP-centred structures towards more collaborative and differentiated approaches to care delivery. This suggests that existing role definitions and organisational frameworks may no longer fully reflect health professionals' evolving self-understanding, innovative potential, and willingness to contribute actively to broader system goals.

Overall, this dissertation underscores the significant potential of team-oriented care models, shaped by the expressed preferences and attitudes of health professionals, for strengthening primary care in Switzerland. The insights provided offer practical guidance for policymakers, educators, healthcare providers, and researchers aiming to design and implement sustainable care models.

Ultimately, this dissertation enriches the academic understanding of professional preferences in primary care and contributes meaningfully to the critical debate on redesigning healthcare systems that are responsive to demographic trends, increasing service demands, and the professional realities of care providers.

1.8 References

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**CHAPTER 2 Professional Beliefs of Physicians and Allied
Health Professionals and Their Willingness to Promote Health
in Primary Care: A Cross-Sectional Survey**

**CHAPTER 3 Health Professionals' Willingness to Share
Responsibility and Strengthen Interprofessional Collaboration:
A Cross-Sectional Survey**

CHAPTER 4 Innovative Capacity of Health Professionals: Results of a National Cross-Sectional Survey in Switzerland

CHAPTER 5 Further Publications

Obsan Report

Brandt, S. K., Essig, S., & Balthasar, A. (2023). *Future Primary Care: Attitudes and Preferences of Health Professionals from Selected Professional Groups* (original title in German: *Zukünftige ambulante Grundversorgung: Einstellungen und Präferenzen von Medizinal- und Gesundheitsfachpersonen ausgewählter Berufsgruppen*), Obsan Report 06/2023. Neuchâtel: Swiss Health Observatory. https://www.obsan.admin.ch/sites/default/files/2023-06/Obsan_06_2023_BERICHT.pdf

Policy Brief

Brandt, S. K., Essig, S., & Balthasar, A. (2024). *Outpatient Care in 2040: What Health Professionals Hope for* (original title in German: *Ambulante Versorgung 2040: Was sich Medizinal- und Gesundheitsfachpersonen wünschen*), Policy Brief. Swiss Learning Health System. https://www.slhs.ch/media/yzjfq3vj/policy-brief_sophie-brandt.pdf

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

Appendix A: Example of Choice Set in the Survey

This example of a choice set in the survey has been translated into English.

Feature	Model 1	Model 2
Responsibility for first contact	Nurse	Pharmacist
Responsibility for developing and implementing treatment plan	General practitioner	Medical practice assistant
Type of decision-making	The professionals involved decide together	A single professional decides
Organisational form	Single practice	Health network

Which model of care do you prefer for patients such as Ms Widmer?

Appendix B: Confirmation of Author Contributions

The contributions of the co-authors are described in the corresponding '*Authors' contributions section*' in each study. As part of the publication process, the contributions have been confirmed by all co-authors. Stefan Essig (S.E.) and Andreas Balthasar (A.B.) are co-authors alongside myself, Sophie Karoline Brandt (S.K.B.).

I confirm that the contributions are accurate.

Author contribution study I (as published):

S.K.B. designed the study, collected, analysed, and interpreted the data, prepared, and revised the manuscript. S.E. designed and supervised the study, advised on data analysis and interpretation, and revised the manuscript. B.A. designed and supervised the study and revised the manuscript. All authors approved the final version of the manuscript.

Author contribution study II (as published):

S.K.B.: Conceptualization; data curation; formal analysis; funding acquisition; investigation; methodology; project administration; visualization; writing – original draft; writing – review and editing. S.E.: Conceptualization; investigation; methodology; project administration; writing – original draft; writing – review and editing. A.B.: Conceptualization; funding acquisition; investigation; project administration; supervision; writing – review and editing.

Author contribution study III (as submitted):

S.K.B. designed the study, collected, analysed, and interpreted the data, prepared, and revised the manuscript. S.E. designed and supervised the study, advised on data analysis and interpretation, and revised the manuscript. B.A. designed and supervised the study and revised the manuscript. All authors approved the final version of the manuscript.

Appendix C: Disclosure Regarding the Use of Artificial Intelligence Tools

During the preparation of chapter 1, the artificial intelligence-based language models ChatGPT (GPT-4 and GPT-5, OpenAI) and Claude (Sonnet 4, Anthropic) were used as supportive tools. Their application was limited to language refinement, translation between German and English, and generating structural suggestions for sections and headings. All content, arguments and interpretations in chapter 1 were developed independently by the author of this dissertation.

For chapters 2, 3, and 4 (peer-reviewed or submitted articles), DeepL Write (DeepL SE, Cologne, Germany) was used exclusively for English-language editing, including orthography, grammar correction, and readability enhancement. All scientific content and interpretations were developed by the respective co-authors as indicated in Appendix B, without artificial intelligence assistance in content generation.

For chapter 5 (further publications), no artificial intelligence tools were used during preparation, writing, or editing processes.

All artificial intelligence outputs were critically reviewed, edited, and integrated where appropriate. The author takes full responsibility for the content presented in this dissertation.